

Graphical Abstract

Intent-driven Orchestration of Serverless Applications in the Computing Continuum

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Highlights

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- Intent-driven orchestration approach for serverless applications.
- Serverless applications deployment and management over multi-cluster infrastructure.
- Serverless function chains scheduling across resources in the computing continuum.
- RL-driven autoscaling mechanisms for serverless function chains.

Intent-driven Orchestration of Serverless Applications in the Computing Continuum

Nikos Filinis^a, Ioannis Tzanettis^a, Dimitrios Spatharakis^a, Eleni Fotopoulou^a, Ioannis Dimolitsas^a, Anastasios Zafeiropoulos^a,
Constantinos Vassilakis^a, Symeon Papavassiliou^a

^a*School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, 10682, Greece*

Abstract

Following the emergence of Internet of Things (IoT) and edge computing technologies and the development of distributed applications with strict Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, a transition is underway from centralized computing models to distributed computing continuum systems. The latter provide abstractions of the available resources, while they lead to the development of orchestration mechanisms with increased distributed intelligence and autonomy characteristics. These characteristics make the computing continuum suitable for managing serverless computing applications, considering their loose coupling with the resources and the need for reactivity and efficiency to serve dynamic workloads in the edge and cloud part of the infrastructure. This paper presents an intent-based approach for the orchestration of a function chain over an edge and cloud infrastructure. We propose a Reinforcement Learning (RL) based autoscaling method that incorporates a reward function that aims to provide optimal utilization of resources and timely autoscaling of the functions, taking advantage of methods for workload prediction. Based on a high-level intent, the proposed optimization problem dictates the scheduling of the functions, minimizing the communication overhead and transformation cost while also considering the energy efficiency of the infrastructure. The proposed solution is evaluated with other state-of-the-art techniques for autoscaling and scheduling of serverless functions in a small edge infrastructure. Our solution provides 1.52% QoS violations with a slight increase in the deployed resources, while also significantly reducing the total cost and power consumption for the deployment of the function chain.

Keywords: Serverless Computing, Computing Continuum, Intent-driven Orchestration, Reinforcement Learning, Service Level Objective, Multi-cluster Scheduling

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1. Introduction

Following the trend for the development of microservices-based applications, approaches that consider the integration of edge and cloud computing management frameworks are emerging, where unified management of resources that span across the computing continuum is considered [1, 2]. With the term computing continuum, we refer to resources that may belong to different parts of the infrastructure, from the Internet of Things (IoT) to the edge to the cloud part of it. The objective is to provide solutions that can optimally serve strict Quality of Service (QoS) requirements of distributed applications, focusing on their latency-sensitive parts that have to be usually provided at the edge, close to their consumption point. For instance, such applications are being developed in the domains of emergency communications, disaster management, remote healthcare, and augmented and virtual reality, where there is often a need to serve distributed Machine Learning (ML)-driven workflows and support tight interaction between IoT and edge computing nodes [3].

The transition to computing continuum systems is highly related to the development of serverless computing applications [4, 5]. In serverless computing, individual functions or microservices are independently deployed and scaled following

the flow of requests by end users, while they may constitute part of an overall application/service chain. Part of the functions can be delay-intolerant and have to be optimally offered at the edge computing part of the infrastructure, while another part can be computationally expensive and can be optimally offered at the cloud computing part of the infrastructure. Management of bursty workloads has to be supported, imposing a need for fast and effective scalability solutions [4]. Moreover, the optimal orchestration of the functions requires solutions that facilitate efficient resource usage while avoiding the over-provisioning of resources, and also considering multiple criteria such as power consumption and the minimization of the total cost for the infrastructure providers [6].

To support the optimal provisioning of serverless applications over resources in the continuum, an integral characteristic of the orchestration approaches to be developed has to do with the proper abstraction of the resources across the continuum from the application developers [5]. This is required, since the resources are not provisioned a priori, like in the case of traditional container or Virtual Machine (VM) based deployments [4] but following the demand by the end users. The resources are also distributed and may span across various clusters, introducing a need for multi-cluster and in some cases multi-cloud management solutions. Therefore, utilizing

Figure 1: High level view of an intent-driven orchestration approach.

intent-driven approaches along with necessary abstractions to declare various requirements bridges the interaction gap between application developers, application providers, and infrastructure providers [7]. Application developers can design their applications considering the ability to declare deployment preferences, requirements, and constraints [4, 8], application providers can define Service Level Objectives (SLOs) in accordance with the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) that they may have with their clients, while infrastructure providers can facilitate these SLOs and optimally serve the provision of the applications.

To this end, another crucial challenge is efficient resource scheduling. This involves finding the optimal mapping of application service functions onto distributed and scattered from edge to cloud, computing and network resources, to meet multiple application- and provider-related objectives [9]. Specifically for serverless computing approaches, the minimization of the applications makespan, which corresponds to the total time taken to process a sequence of functions (application/service chain) for its complete execution, is strongly dependent on optimizing the functions' placement [10]. Moreover, in order to minimize the overall cost for the infrastructure providers and optimize the performance of the function chain, a crucial aspect is also to consider the cold-start delay of serverless functions [11, 12]. Besides, the scheduling of serverless functions in the proximity of IoT devices is key to minimizing network delays. However, optimal placement of the function chains is also necessary to take into consideration the utilization of resources and the energy consumption of the

underlying infrastructure [13].

Based on the aforementioned trends and challenges, in the current manuscript, we introduce an intent-driven orchestration approach for serverless computing applications deployed across the computing continuum. A high level view of the proposed approach is depicted in Figure 1. The applications are represented as a chain of serverless functions. An intent is declared for the optimal provision of the serverless applications. We consider an intent-driven approach to facilitate the description of SLOs on behalf of the clients or the application developers [14] and avoid the strict definition of resources that have to be reserved [4]. Through SLOs awareness, application developers and application providers can influence the execution of serverless functions and support the fulfillment of specific objectives. For instance, an objective to achieve high performance for an application part or an objective for cost reduction can be translated to different deployment plans and runtime orchestration actions. A requirement for the avoidance of cold starts and the associated performance fluctuations can be also declared. Similarly, geolocation constraints can be specified (e.g., imposing collocation of specific serverless functions due to data privacy issues). Such SLOs can be translated to proper SLAs and, subsequently, to deployment plans and orchestration actions applicable across the continuum. A set of challenges arise for the latter part since there is a need for unified management of resources across multiple clusters and -in some cases- collaboration among different application providers. In all cases, focus has to be given to increasing the distributed intelligence and automation

characteristics of the applied orchestration mechanisms.

Summarizing, the main contribution of the work detailed in this manuscript regards:

- An approach for intent-driven orchestration of serverless computing applications, where on one hand we support abstraction of the resources from the application developer, while on the other hand, we provide unified management interfaces for resources that are distributed in various clusters across the continuum.
- A Reinforcement Learning (RL)-driven autoscaling mechanism to decide the number of replicas for each deployed function. Specifically, we propose a reward function that optimizes resource utilization by nominating scaling decisions that provide results closer to the selected SLA. Moreover, an ARIMA-based workload predictor facilitates the timely scaling of the replicas according to the workload demands. To this end, we formulate an RL environment and employ a Deep Q-Network (DQN) based agent that keeps the average latency below a predefined threshold while minimizing the number of replicas for all the functions.
- A Scheduling Optimizer that facilitates the decision of the placement of a function chain in the computing continuum. Specifically, we formulate a multi-objective optimization problem to minimize (a) the link utilization between the edge and cloud infrastructure, (b) the transformation cost which tries to maintain where the function is executed and avoid cold starts, and (c) the power consumption of the system. The proposed method minimizes inter-function communication and start-up delays while also providing an energy-efficient placement decision for the functions, aiming to reduce the costs of the infrastructure providers.
- Evaluation results for the proposed framework based on experiments in a small-scale testbed, including a thorough comparison with other state-of-the-art serverless autoscaling and scheduling techniques. The presented method outperforms the compared ones by having 1.52% QoS violations for the function chain, with a slight increase in the deployed number of replicas. Finally, the proposed scheduling approach reduced the cost and the power consumption significantly.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the relevant works in the literature, considering the areas of intent specification, autoscaling mechanisms for serverless computing platforms and optimal scheduling techniques for multi-cluster deployments. In Section 3, we introduce the system architecture and modeling of the proposed approach, considering both the scheduling and autoscaling part of the serverless functions. In Section 4 we provide the evaluation of the proposed framework under a small-scale testbed and the comparison with other baseline techniques. Finally, Section 5 concludes the manuscript and discusses future research steps.

2. Related Work

2.1. Intent-driven orchestration mechanisms in the computing continuum

Intents are policies written in high-level operational or business objectives that a system should meet [15]. The main idea is, through an intent-based description to specify and communicate to the system how it should behave, without providing details on how it should achieve the objectives. The latter should happen in an autonomous manner, with minimal human intervention, assisted by ML and Artificial Intelligence (AI) mechanisms. This intent-driven model has been recently incorporated into management and orchestration practices.

In [14], Intent-Driven Orchestration (IDO) enables the management of cloud-native applications through their SLOs while minimizing service owner and administrator overhead. Service owners express the desired target Key Performance Indicator (KPI) objectives for their service components instead of declaratively defining the required state and resources, enabling in this way the ease of use and abstraction from underlying platforms. Considering a single provider underlying infrastructure, a Kubernetes-based orchestration stack is enhanced by adding a planning component responsible for translating service objectives into actionable deployment decisions. Comparison of the application state with the desired state during runtime, through the evaluation of an introduced distance metric, triggers decisions on required adjustments to meet the objectives.

Development of efficient intent translation mechanisms becomes quite more challenging when considering the deployment of distributed applications over resources in the continuum [16]. Modelling and monitoring of heterogeneous resources in the various parts of the continuum, proper translation of application requirements, decision making on where the processing should occur and application orchestration become complex tasks to address.

Oakestra [17] is a hierarchical orchestration framework for edge computing that consolidates multiple infrastructure providers and supports applications over dynamic variations at the edge. It organizes the infrastructure into distinct clusters allowing multiple edge operators to contribute their local deployments towards a shared infrastructure as separate clusters with independent administrative control. To deploy applications, developers submit the code along with an SLA descriptor to the system manager component of the architecture. The SLA includes high-level operational requirements and constraints for service execution at the edge, e.g., virtualization, required hardware, geolocation, etc. which must be respected throughout the application lifecycle. Furthermore, developers can fine-tune the precision of scheduling heuristics.

In [18], the authors introduce SLOC - an elasticity framework, which promotes a novel performance-driven, SLO native approach to cloud computing. The SLO-native approach introduces a paradigm shift from general, business logic agnostic, low-level SLAs to intent-based, SLO-first, performance-driven, and orchestration-aware elasticity models.

SLO-first means that all the SLOs and QoS along multiple elasticity dimensions are inherently aligned with application model and business requirements/KPIs as opposed to external, predefined, business logic agnostic configuration. To support intent-focused, multidimensional elasticity models, the framework provides coordination, control, and orchestration approaches that enable cloud platforms to adapt dynamically to varying load patterns in a dependable manner. The authors emphasize the need for a new SLO elasticity policy language to allow developers to define SLOs by referring to their workloads and their components as entities, for which they can define constraints on certain characteristics, e.g., the response time.

In [19], code annotations are used as a powerful means to simplify infrastructural concerns and patterns for developers of Functions as a Service (FaaS)-based applications. By bringing infrastructure-as-code concepts into the function source via powerful code annotations, typical orchestration patterns, such as keeping containerised cloud functions warm to ensure the absence of cold starts, can be simplified. Infrastructural concerns and function execution patterns are wrapped in annotations. During the deployment process code annotations are properly translated and reflected into system configurations where the function is deployed. However, there is a lot of space for meaningful extensions to this promising approach; more patterns should be captured and implemented, context dependent smartness should be studied so that annotations that are not suitable could be overridden by system intelligence, a proper balance among multiple objectives such as green and sustainable serverless computing, secure serverless computing etc. should be pursuit.

In the current manuscript, we adopt principles and specifications provided in the aforementioned research works; each one having a limited scope and specific focus as detailed before and compared in Table 1, and provide an intent specification that requires to have a broader scope and applicability to address deployments across the computing continuum. Towards this direction, we consider specifications for intent-driven resources management in the continuum in our previous work [8]. Based on this work, we consider the description of intent in the form of objectives, properties and constraints that can be defined at node (function or microservice), link or application level.

2.2. Autoscaling in serverless computing

Autoscaling support is considered as one of the main characteristics of serverless computing platforms. Various adaptive autoscaling solutions are made available, considering the need to achieve high performance under dynamic workloads and low cost based on conservative resource usage. A set of challenges have to be tackled [31, 20, 32]. These include the need to manage the latency introduced through the cold start of functions based on their invocation for the first time, the specification of the granularity of scaling decisions to achieve a balance between an under and an over-provisioning of resources, the specification of the main triggering points for scaling decisions taking into account a rest period and potential

oscillation effects, and the impact of scaling of specific actions to the overall performance of the function chain.

The provided solutions can be classified as proactive and reactive. A majority of them is taking advantage of ML techniques and especially RL [20, 21], while other approaches are also based on the specification of threshold-based rules (e.g., concurrency value and the rate of requests per second) [22]. Authors in [21] propose an RL approach to perform autoscaling for serverless environments. The discussed self-learning algorithm tries to identify the most suitable scaling decision by utilizing the dependency of throughput and latency to the concurrency level. In [22] the authors propose analytical performance models for contemporary serverless computing platforms, specifically those utilizing concurrency values and request rates for autoscaling decisions, such as Knative and Google Cloud Run. Two dynamic RL strategies, for VM autoscaling are discussed in [23]. By utilizing fuzzy logic, and combining an off-policy with an on-policy learning algorithm, the authors implemented a controller to perform real-time decision-making for autoscaling resources, aiming to meet the response time requirements while minimizing application's cost. In our case, we build upon our previous work [20], where we have developed a set of RL environments and agents (based on Q-learning, DynaQ+ and Deep Q-learning algorithms) for driving autoscaling mechanisms, able to autonomously manage dynamic workloads with QoS guarantees, while opting for efficient usage of resources.

In the current manuscript, this work has been extended to consider resources made available in a multi-cluster infrastructure, as well as the management of autoscaling of serverless function chains instead of a single function. In this way, the dependencies among the functions in a chain has to be modeled and considered in the analysis part, while the evaluation is based on the achievement of end-to-end performance indicators for the overall function chain.

2.3. Distributed Functions Scheduling in the computing continuum

In the context of the computing continuum, serverless functions can be strategically placed and executed across multiple layers, encompassing the edge, and cloud domains. An Integer Linear Programming (ILP) formulation for the embedding of chained virtual functions in the computing continuum is proposed in [24]. Focusing on enhancing the application's resilience, the proposed model prioritizes the more utilized computing nodes to embed several requests for chained virtual functions, while a heuristic is introduced to handle scenarios of higher complexity, involving embedding on multiple tiers of the continuum. The distributed placement of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) that compose a service chain is discussed in [25]. Santos et al. [27], proposed a Service Function Chaining (SFC) controller that undertakes the distributed placement of SFCs in the computing continuum focusing on delay minimization. With reference to Kubernetes [33], two node selection policies are determined, (i) the latency-aware, where the node for pod placement is selected based on calculations of a shortest-path-based algorithm, and (ii)

Table 1: Related work comparison.

Attributes	Related Works															Proposed Study
	[14]	[17]	[18]	[19]	[20]	[21]	[22]	[23]	[24]	[25]	[26]	[27]	[28]	[29]	[30]	
Intent-Driven Orchestration	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓
Edge-Cloud Orchestration	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	✓
ML Orchestration	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓
Service Function Chaining	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FaaS Orchestration	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓
Service Placement	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Latency Minimization	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Migration	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	✓
Autoscaling Support	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	✓
Power Efficiency	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓

the location-aware, in which the selection is performed by the *TargetNode* location preference of the pod's configuration file. Energy saving and delay guarantees are considered for VNF placement and routing by Varasteh et al. [28]. The paper introduces an ILP formulation of the problem, taking into account the power consumption models of physical machines and network switches, along with their resource constraints. By decomposing it into two subproblems, a heuristic named Holu, deals with the complexity of the discussed problem. Also, the routing of the VNF chain is performed by employing Lagrange Relaxation, and the shortest path that traverses the nodes that the VNFs are hosted in, is identified. Authors in [26], propose a scalable hybrid reinforcement learning approach to manage cloud infrastructures. The RL strategy within a hybrid architecture aims to minimize the SLA violations in the applications response time under dynamic workloads. The proposed decision-making approach regarding VM migration, chooses a target node to host a VM, in a way that brings response time within SLA level. However, the suggested strategy does not undertake the initial VM placement while no SFC characteristics are considered. In [29], a path-based approach constructs a set of candidate embedding paths on which hybrid-SFCs can be hosted towards round-trip delay minimization. An initial VNF mapping heuristic of mixed placement policy ensures the resource capacity constraints for a dynamic virtual network embedding request and the distributed solution constructed in polynomial time achieves near-optimal solutions. Focusing exclusively on Function as a Service (FaaS), authors in [30] introduce a model, which focuses on efficient and scalable placement of FaaS-based service functions to manage the lifecycle of applications in the computing continuum. The proposed framework, leverages monitoring data regarding microservices invocations, domain resource capacity, and application-related QoS metrics, and performs a domain selection for the placement of microservices, by unifying weighted scores regarding the total service latency and battery consumption of the device.

Most scheduling approaches are integrated into orchestration frameworks for different application development models with varying objectives, as presented in Table 1. However, a few of them identify the set of KPIs to match the dynamic features of compute continuum resource management. By considering these works, in the current manuscript we detail a multi-

objective optimization problem that computes a scheduling strategy in order to satisfy the defined SLOs that constitute the intent provided by the end user. Focus is given on objectives related to performance to achieve conformance to SLAs and energy aspects.

3. Intent-driven Orchestration Approach

3.1. Service Level Objectives Awareness

We consider an approach where the computational and network resources in the continuum are abstracted from the application developers and providers. Through resources abstraction, there is no need for the declaration of resources for the deployment of serverless applications, simplifying the deployment process, especially in cases of deployments across heterogeneous clusters. In this way, high level objectives, properties and constraints can be specified during development time. This set of information is considered as the deployment intent and can be associated with one or more SLOs. As detailed in Section 2.1, recent works are considering the development of specific intent handlers and translation mechanisms for this purpose [14, 15, 16]. Based on the described intent and the mapping with SLOs, orchestration mechanisms are developed that target to achieve the desired intent or state based on optimal deployment and runtime adjustments.

The high level objectives are defined based on the offerings provided by application providers. It can be related to high performance (e.g., p99 compliance in latency, high throughput), high availability, high reliability, network isolation, energy efficient operation and/or cost reduction. Properties may refer to specific characteristics that have to be supported by functions or links (e.g., autoscaling with maximum number of replicas autoscaling:true, max-pods:5). Configurations in terms of cold-start management and scale-to-zero aspects can be denoted as properties, as well as aspects related to concurrency limits of the serverless functions. Specific constraints can be declared related to the locations where the deployment of each function may take place (e.g., collocation of functions in the same cluster, deployment in a trusted execution environment). The constraints can be classified as soft or hard constraints, based on the way that they can be interpreted during deployment and runtime. Hard constraints have to be satisfied by all means

```

apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Intent
metadata:
  name: my-app-intent
spec:
  targetRef:
    kind: "Deployment"
    name: "default/my-app-deployment"
  objectives:
    - name: my-app-p95compliance // P-95 latency compliance
      // target of less than 15ms
      value: 15
      measuredBy: myapp/p95latency
    - name: my-app-energyfootprint // improvement based on
      // the business as usual (BaU)
      value: '20'
      measuredBy: myapp/totalpower
  properties:
    - name: my-function1-concurrency // serve a maximum
      // of 100 concurrent requests
      value: '100'
      measuredBy: myapp/function1/concurrency
  constraints:
    - name: my-function2-geolocation
      value: 'edge-cluster-1'

```

Figure 2: Sample intent description.

during the application’s deployment and operation, while soft constraints can be treated in a best-effort manner.

We consider that the intent can be made available in the form of metadata integrated or associated with an application descriptor. For instance, an indicative intent description is provided in Figure 2 where objectives, properties, and constraints associated with an application are declared in a structured form. This serves as an abstract declaration of the expectations regarding the application’s deployment and runtime, to be fulfilled in the implementation phase of the application and assured during the application’s lifetime. In the exhibited indicative sample description, first, the targeted application (description) is specified (under the “targetRef” field) while then two high-level objectives are declared (under the “objectives” field) to achieve a p95 compliance with a latency value of 15ms (95% of the time the latency should be below the defined value) and an improvement in terms of energy efficiency by 20% (compared to a Business as Usual (BaU) scenario). Then, a property regarding the maximum number of requests allowed to be served concurrently by a specified function is set to a value of 100 (under the “properties” field). At the same time, a constraint is declared (under the “constraints” field) regarding the geographical area where a specified function is required to be deployed. In all cases of declarations referring to a measurable quantity assigned with a target or bounding value, the evaluation process is referenced (under the “measuredBy” sub-field).

3.2. System Architecture

In this section, we present an intent-driven orchestration framework for the scaling and scheduling of serverless applications. We assume that the deployed application comprises several serverless functions that construct a linear function chain as in [34]. We assume a multi-cluster computing environment that consists of two layers, namely; an edge infrastructure and a cloud infrastructure. For each

infrastructure, we consider that there exists a dedicated server to facilitate the scheduling of the serverless functions, activated only if required. The edge and cloud infrastructure communicate via layer-3 routers and switches that provide a static link, ensuring connectivity from the access layer at the edge to the core. However, additional communication delay occurs during data transmission from the edge to the cloud through the backhaul and the core network [35], requiring efficient function placement and traffic routing. Moreover, a time-varying incoming workload for the specific function chain arrives at the edge for processing. The edge infrastructure is considered in the proximity of the users’ (function chain) requests. As a result, the end-to-end latency benefits from the scheduling of functions at the edge server, which however has a limited capacity, and thus, a hybrid deployment model leveraging resource capabilities of both the edge and the cloud is often the most viable solution under many practical scenarios [6]. For the deployment of the specific function chain, we consider a high-level intent description expressing objectives regarding three identified Key Performance Indicators of the systems’ performance, i.e., (a) the SLA of the latency, (b) the link utilization delay between the edge and the cloud and (c) the total power consumption of the infrastructure. A high-level system architecture of the system is depicted in Figure 3.

The orchestration of the functions is performed by a serverless framework; in our case, we chose OpenFaas¹ as we conducted the experiments in a self-hosted infrastructure as it will be further explained in Section 4. Furthermore, to enable communication between the two computing infrastructures we utilize Liqo² as an open-source multi-cluster management tool. Our system operates in time slots, a solution that is common in autoscaling methods to avoid oscillation phenomena for the instantiation of the functions [36].

The main components of the proposed framework are introduced here and thoroughly explained in the following sections:

- **Workload Estimator:** We utilize a time-series forecasting method, i.e., ARIMA, to predict the number of incoming requests $\bar{\lambda}$, of the time-varying workload, for the next time slot. We utilize this prediction to provide proactive decisions for the scaling and scheduling of the serverless functions.
- **RL-based Autoscaling:** We employ an RL-driven autoscaling technique to compute the number of replicas for each function of the function chain. This way, we guarantee that the average delay of the estimated requests is under a predefined threshold, while the number of deployed replicas is minimized avoiding the overprovisioning of resources. To compute the scaling decision a DQN method is utilized taking also into consideration the current systems’ performance. The DQN agent is trained offline with a training dataset

¹<https://www.openfaas.com/>

²<https://liqo.io/>

Figure 3: System Architecture.

and captures the dynamicity of the state while a reward function expresses the intent for the SLA of the latency.

- **Scheduling Optimizer:** Then the scaling decision is sent to the Scheduling Optimizer to orchestrate the scheduling of the replicas of the functions to the edge and cloud server. We formulate a multi-objective optimization problem that computes a scheduling strategy in order to satisfy the systems' intents. To this end, we try to minimize (a) the link utilization between the edge and the cloud (b) the transformation cost which indirectly minimizes the delay by reducing the number of cold starts of the functions, and (c) the total power utilization of the underlying infrastructure.

Finally, during the lifetime of the function chain, the metrics collected from the serverless framework, the traffic metrics, and the performance metrics of the functions framework are stored in the monitoring system that is Prometheus³ in our case.

3.3. System Modeling

In this section, we provide the system modeling of the proposed framework. Let $\{f_1 \dots f_n\}$, be the set of functions that comprises the function chain. We consider that the resources on the edge server have a finite capacity, i.e., C_E denotes the maximum available vCPUs and R_E the maximum available memory resources. Similarly, C_C and R_C denote the maximum available vCPUs and memory resources on the cloud server. For each function, we consider a set of predefined resources defined as a tuple $\langle c_i, r_i \rangle$ for CPU and memory respectively. We model the workflow of the function chain as a graph $G_f = (V_f, E_f)$. The vertices in the graph represent each function $V_f = \{f_i \mid i = 0 \dots n\}$, where f_0 indicates the ingress point for the traffic incoming to the edge. The edges between the nodes, i.e., $E_f = \{f_i \rightarrow f_j \mid j = i + 1, 1 \leq i, j \leq n\}$ represent the order of execution of the chain meaning that e.g., f_j is executed

after f_i . We assume that the output of the last function f_n must arrive at the ingress point f_0 , hence G_f is a cycle. As a result, the path of the function chain is $F = \{f_0, f_1, \dots, f_n, f_{n+1}\}$, where $f_{n+1} = f_0$. To address the varying workload λ and maintain a certain QoS, we consider that multiple replicas s_i , $i = 1 \dots n$ of the same function can be instantiated in the edge or the cloud. We define the function scaling matrix as $\mathbf{s} = [s_1 \dots s_n]$, for $i = 1 \dots n$. Moreover, we define the maximum number of replicas for each function s^{max} where $s_i \leq s^{max}$, for $i = 1 \dots n$. Let x_i for $i = 0 \dots n + 1$, be a binary decision variable, to denote the scheduling of the replicas of each function

$$x_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ function is placed in the cloud} \\ 0, & \text{the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ function is placed in the edge} \end{cases}$$

where $x_0 = x_{n+1} = 0$ to indicate that the ingress node is placed in the edge. We now define the function's scheduling matrix as $\mathbf{x} = [x_1 \dots x_n]$, for $i = 1 \dots n$. Moreover, let y_i for $i = 0 \dots n$ be a binary variable to indicate if two successive functions are collocated:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x_i = x_{i+1} \\ 1, & \text{if } x_i \neq x_{i+1} \end{cases}$$

For example, if $y_i = 0$ then the functions f_i and f_{i+1} are placed in the same server. In this work we assume that the inter-server communication between functions is considered negligible. Figure 4 depicts an example of scheduling four serverless functions in the continuum. The chain follows the path $\{f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4\}$. The ingress and the egress points of the network traffic are placed on the edge and are denoted as f_0 and f_5 respectively, thus $x_0 = x_5 = 0$. The corresponding parameters regarding the placement and the collocation of the functions are also illustrated. Moreover, we assume that all of the replicas for each function are collocated either in the edge or in the cloud. Finally, let ξ_E and ξ_C be two binary variables to indicate if the edge and the cloud servers are required in order

³<https://prometheus.io/>

Figure 4: A scheduling example of four chained serverless functions in the computing continuum.

to deploy the function chain:

$$\xi_E = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{edge is active, if } \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - x_i) > 0 \\ 0, & \text{edge is inactive, otherwise} \end{cases},$$

$$\xi_C = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{cloud is active, if } \sum_{i=1}^n x_i > 0 \\ 0, & \text{cloud is inactive, otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

We now define the three metrics of our system. The expected output of each function (in MB as in [28]) is denoted with d_i for $i = 0 \dots n + 1$ and is the input to the next function in the chain F . So, we define the communication delay between the functions as follows:

$$t_i = y_i \cdot \frac{\bar{\lambda} \cdot d_i}{R}, \quad \text{for } i = 0 \dots n, \quad (1)$$

where R is the communication rate of the fiber link between the edge and the cloud and $\bar{\lambda}$ is the prediction produced by the Workload Estimator, i.e., the ARIMA forecasting.

1. *Link Utilization Delay*: The total link utilization delay between the functions of the chain is given by:

$$T(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=0}^n y_i \cdot t_i. \quad (2)$$

By introducing this metric, we promote scheduling solutions that allow the consecutive functions in the chain to be collocated in the computing infrastructure. This is a common technique to reduce the total communication delay of the chain by avoiding multiple traversals of the physical link between the edge and the cloud [37]. However, due to limited resources at the edge, a balance between edge and cloud placement is necessary [38]. As a result, we assume that the link utilization delay is a system metric that we need to minimize to achieve better performance.

As said previously, the dynamic resource orchestration of serverless applications suffers from the cold start delay. For example, if an application is currently deployed on the edge and must be migrated to the cloud, a non-significant overhead in the delay occurs. As a result, in order to quantify a system cost to reduce such transitions that result in frequent cold start overheads we introduce the following cost.

2. *Transformation Cost*: The total transformation cost of the function chain is defined as follows:

$$C(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left((\alpha \cdot (x_i - x_i^{prev}) + \beta) \cdot |x_i - x_i^{prev}| \right), \quad (3)$$

where x_i^{prev} is the previous scheduling of function f_i , and α, β are tunable parameters to penalize the migration from the edge to the cloud and vice versa. For example, using the Eq. (3) in case of a function f_1 which was deployed in the cloud, i.e., $x_1 = 1$ the transformation cost of transferring to the edge, i.e., $x_1 = 0$, $x_1^{prev} = 0$ is $C(f_1) = (\alpha \cdot (-1) + \beta) \cdot |-1| = -\alpha + \beta$. Naturally, if no migration is needed then this cost is zero. The reasoning of this function is to try to keep the functions of the chain "warm", meaning that the cold start phenomena are minimized.

Finally, we introduce the final metric regarding the power consumption of the deployed functions. Following [39] we predict the power consumption model of a server based on its CPU utilization u .

$$P = \delta \cdot P_{MAX} + (1 - \delta) \cdot P_{MAX} \cdot u, \quad (4)$$

where δ parameter indicates the ratio (typically 60%, [40]) of consumed power of a server in idle state w.r.t. to the maximum power consumption P_{MAX} . Following Eq. (4) we proceed on defining the power consumption of the function chain's F . The total power consumption of all functions subject to the scheduling and CPU utilization of the respective resources (i.e., edge or cloud server) of each respective function is given by:

$$P_F = (1 - \delta) \cdot (\xi_E \cdot P_{MAX}^E) \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left((1 - x_i) \cdot c_i \cdot s_i \right)}{C_E} + (1 - \delta) \cdot (\xi_C \cdot P_{MAX}^C) \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i \cdot c_i \cdot s_i)}{C_C}. \quad (5)$$

Therefore, based on Eq. (4) and (5), we can define the final metric of the system.

3. *Power Consumption*: The total power consumption of the function chain is given by:

$$P_F^{total}(\mathbf{x}) = (\xi_C \cdot P_{MAX}^C + \xi_E \cdot P_{MAX}^E) \cdot \delta + P_F, \quad (6)$$

where P_{MAX}^E and P_{MAX}^C are the maximum power consumption of the edge and cloud server respectively. To this end, we formulate the total cost of the system as a weighted sum of the metrics.

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}) = w_T \cdot T(\mathbf{x}) + w_C \cdot C(\mathbf{x}) + w_P \cdot P_F^{total}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (7)$$

where $w_T, w_C, w_P \in \mathcal{R}^+$ are tunable positive parameters for the network delay, transformation cost, and total power consumption respectively. By properly choosing the values of these parameters, one can express the relationship between high-level intents for different KPIs of the system. Moreover, we should note that the edge infrastructure is considered to provide less communication overhead. However, due to the resource capacity of the edge server, the function chain is not necessarily prioritized to be placed at the edge.

Figure 5: RL-driven function autoscaler.

3.4. RL-driven Autoscaling of Serverless Functions

RL has been proven to have great potential for solving control problems in complex, uncertain environments. It is a promising approach for managing autoscaling in the cloud [41] and serverless contexts [20] compared to existing — more static- rule-based approaches. In the current manuscript, an RL environment has been formulated so as to interoperate efficiently with the orchestration infrastructure. Using historical traces collected by a random-based agent, a Deep Q-Network agent was trained and deployed as an autonomous intelligent orchestration mechanism capable of meeting the requirements translated from the declared deployment intent. Figure 5 depicts how both the environment and the agent interact between them as well as with the rest of the orchestration components. The *DQN agent* receives the reward and the state from the environment and proposes a specific scaling action to the *Scaling controller*. The *Scaling controller* communicates with the *Scheduling Optimizer* who decides where the functions are going to be deployed (to the edge or the cloud). Both information (replicas and placement plan) are given to the *Multi-cluster* orchestrator, who enforces the deployment and feeds constantly the *Monitoring System* with fresh metrics. The Environment refreshes its state based on the current metrics coming from the *Monitoring System* and the predicted workload generated by the *Workload Estimator* while it calculates the new reward for the Agent. The RL environment and the DQN agent are both described below.

In the current manuscript, we have designed a continuous state - discrete action Reinforcement Learning environment capable of taking actions regarding the exact replicas each serverless function should have at any given moment in order to achieve the SLOs defined at the intent-driven orchestration infrastructure. Through the reward function, the environment can guide any agent to achieve an expected learning that consists of minimizing the allocated resources of the serverless functions (number of replicas/pods) while at the same time conforming to the agreed SLA, which in our case is a reference latency where application works optimally.

As mentioned in [42], the problem can be formulated as

a Markov Decision Process (MDP) where an agent leverages information about the current state of the environment to take an action. A Markov Decision Process is identified by a tuple $\langle S, A, P, R, \gamma \rangle$, where S is the state of the environment, A is the set of possible actions, P is the state transition probability function $P : S \times A \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$, R is the reward function $R : S \times A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and γ is the discount factor whose value denotes how important future or immediate rewards are. The goal of the agent is to learn a policy π that represents the probability of selecting an action given that the environment is at a certain state. The state-value function Q is employed to quantify how beneficial the enforcement of each action a is at a given state s by calculating the expected value of the sum of the discounted future rewards if the policy π is followed by the agent:

$$Q_{\pi}(s, a) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k R_{t+k+1} \mid S_t = s, A_t = a \right] \quad (8)$$

The update rule for the value of the Q function is as follows:

$$Q'(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow (1 - \alpha) \cdot Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha \cdot (r_t + \gamma \cdot \max_a Q(s_{t+1}, a)) \quad (9)$$

where α denotes the learning rate of the algorithm.

For the state of the environment, we consider the number of replicas s_i allocated to each function i , the incoming traffic load λ of the workload measured in requests per second, and the corresponding measured end-to-end latency d . Additionally, we include in the state of the environment the predicted workload, i.e., $\bar{\lambda}$ provided by the *Workload Estimator* component. To this end, the RL environment incorporates the workload pattern and facilitates the proactive scaling of the functions. Therefore, the state space dimension is as follows:

$$\text{State space: } s_1 \times s_2 \times \dots \times s_n \times \lambda \times \bar{\lambda} \times d,$$

As for the agent's available actions, we consider scaling in and out actions by one replica for each function i (i.e. $a_i = \{-1, 0, +1\}$). (+1) means that the serverless function should add one more replica, (-1) means that the serverless function should remove one replica and (0) means that the serverless function maintains the same replicas as before.

$$\text{Action space: } a_1 \times a_2 \times \dots \times a_n,$$

The reward returned from the environment to the agent takes into consideration the latency-resources trade-off and thus, tries to minimize the latency metric and in parallel keep the replicas allocated to a minimum. In order to account for invalid scaling actions that may be attempted, we consider a very low reward $R_{pen} = -100$ to keep the agent away from them (e.g., when the serverless function has achieved the maximum allocated pods, then the (+1) action is considered inappropriate). In order to sufficiently penalize SLA violations we also give a very negative reward $R_{pen} = -100$ in such states (e.g., when the current latency is higher than the reference/desired latency). All the above is expressed by the following two-part equation:

Figure 6: Latency reward.

$$R_{total} = \begin{cases} R_{pen}, & \text{if action invalid and SLO is unreached} \\ w_{lat} \cdot R_{lat} + w_{res} \cdot R_{res}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (10)$$

The weights w_{lat} and w_{res} are assigned to each part of the trade-off. The R_{lat} represents the reward calculated based on the current latency and the R_{res} represents the reward calculated based on the number of replicas of each serverless function. R_{total} is used to calculate a weighted average of the two parts.

Regarding the latency part of Eq. (10), we formulate the following function:

$$R_{lat}(z) = \begin{cases} R_{max} \cdot e^{-0.06 \cdot g \cdot (ref-z)^2}, & \text{if } z \leq ref \\ R_{max} \cdot e^{-10 \cdot g \cdot (ref-z)^2}, & \text{if } ref < z \leq 1 \end{cases}, \quad (11)$$

where $z = \frac{d}{obj}$, with d representing the current measured end-to-end latency, obj is the desired latency agreed on the SLA declared by the intent, and $ref \in (0, 1)$ is a hyperparameter that is set empirically close to 0.8. This hyper-parameter is selected to penalize proactively actions that are getting too close to the reference SLA with the risk of overpassing it. The function is depicted in Figure 6. Specifically, Eq. (11) reaches the maximum value of $R_{max} = 100$ when the reference value of the SLA is reached, i.e., $z = ref$. However, the function steeply decreases exponentially ($e^{-10 \cdot g}$) approximating to the minimum value (set to 0), if the desired SLA threshold is violated, while it has a smoother decrease in the reward ($e^{-0.06 \cdot g}$) towards zero when the current latency is lower than the reference. The latter, allows the agent to learn efficiently to avoid excessively low latency values. Besides, that would result in higher costs as the number of replicas would be increased while the SLA is already satisfied, and the suboptimal utilization of resources, i.e., under-provisioning of the replicas. The choice of all the parameters aims to normalize the reward function between the values $[-100, 100]$ to assist the agent in learning optimal policies according to the state. Moreover, the hyper-parameter g is set to 5 to balance the steepness of the slope, however, evaluated in subsection 4.4.

The second part of Eq. (10) represents the reward for the used resources (the active number of replicas) and is given in Eq. (12).

$$R_{res}(\mathbf{s}) = \frac{R_{max}}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{s_{max} - s_i}{s_{max} - 1}, \quad (12)$$

where s_{max} is the maximum number of replicas for a function and s_i is the current number of replicas deployed for each function. The relationship between the reward and the number of deployed resources is linear with the reward receiving the maximum value R_{max} when $s_i = 1$ and the minimum value when $s_i = s_{max}$ for function i , for $i = 1 \dots n$.

Regarding the implemented RL agent, the DQN algorithm [43] was adopted to the aforementioned environment model. The neural network of the agent consists of an input layer of $n+3$ inputs, 2 hidden layers with L_1 and L_2 neurons accordingly and an output layer of 3^n outputs. This is illustrated in Figure 5. The agent receives the reward and the state from the environment and uses the neural network to estimate the target Q-value for the current state using the *Forward* method. Based on this value, the *Update* method then updates the weights of the network by also using the received reward. The Q-values of the current state for all the actions are evaluated and the best action is selected with the use of an *epsilon-greedy* policy. The selected action is then returned to the *Scaling controller* of the environment.

3.5. Scheduling Optimizer of Serverless Functions

Following the scaling decision $\mathbf{s} = [s_1 \dots s_n]$ computed by the RL-driven Autoscaling agent, it is time to introduce the last component of our framework, namely; the Scheduling Optimizer. To acquire a scheduling decision for the serverless functions we formulate the following optimization problem:

$$\mathcal{E}1 : \min_{\mathbf{x}} \Psi(\mathbf{x}) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - x_i) \cdot s_i c_i \leq C_E \quad (13a)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (1 - x_i) \cdot s_i r_i \leq R_E \quad (13b)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot s_i c_i \leq C_C \quad (13c)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot s_i r_i \leq R_C \quad (13d)$$

$$x_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i = 1 \dots n \quad (13e)$$

In problem $\mathcal{E}1$, Constraints (13a) and (13b) guarantee that the total deployed replicas of the function in the edge infrastructure do not exceed the available capacity in resources in terms of CPU and memory respectively. Similarly, Constraints (13c) and (13d) guarantee that the replicas of the functions deployed in the cloud do not exceed the available capacities. Finally, Constraint (13e) defines that a function, and all of its replicas,

are deployed either in the edge or the cloud infrastructure. Problem $\mathcal{E}1$ is a mixed integer linear program, which is generally NP-hard, and the lower bound of the computational complexity of the branch-and-cut algorithm used to find a solution is exponential [44]. However, for the specific setup used in this work, i.e., the functions are deployed either on the edge or the cloud, it is feasible to extract a near-optimal solution (or the optimal one for a relatively small number of functions) with low execution time using an open-source solver e.g., Gurobi⁴. Besides, as stated in [45], 82% of the serverless applications consists of five functions. The benefit of using Eq. (7) as the objective function is threefold. First, the Scheduling Optimizer will nominate scheduling decisions that involve only the edge infrastructure, to minimize the communication delay of the cloud. Naturally, when the requested resources are exceeded at the edge, the cloud will be utilized, however by minimizing the communication delay between the functions due to Eq. (2). Second, cold start phenomena will be reduced by nominating solutions with low transformation cost (Eq. (3)). Finally, the scheduling solution accounts also for the minimum power consumption of the system, through Eq. (6). Upon calculating the scheduling decision, the Scheduling Optimizer dictates the serverless platform to instantiate the respective number of replicas in the appropriate server. In Algorithm 1 we provide the workflow of the proposed method.

Algorithm 1: Complete Algorithm Flow

- 1: **Input:** Application graph F , Intent formulation \mathcal{I}
 - 2: **Offline training:**
 - 3: **for** workload λ in test dataset **do**
 - 4: stress graph F with λ
 - 5: collect performance data of graph F
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: Train DQN agent offline based on the collected data and the Intent \mathcal{I}
 - 8: **Learnt policy deployment:**
 - 9: Instantiate application graph F
 - 10: **for** each timeslot **do**
 - 11: $\bar{\lambda} \leftarrow$ forecast the incoming workload using the workload predictor
 - 12: $d \leftarrow$ measure the latency in the previous timeslot
 - 13: $(s, \lambda, \bar{\lambda}, d) \leftarrow$ observe current environment state
 - 14: $A_t \leftarrow$ RL-driven function autoscaler chooses the best action greedily
 - 15: $s \leftarrow$ update replica count
 - 16: $x \leftarrow$ Scheduling Optimizer decides placement solving Problem (13)
 - 17: Deploy the new s depending on placement x
 - 18: **end for**
-

⁴<https://www.gurobi.com/>

Figure 7: Experimentation workload.

4. Implementation and Performance Evaluation

In this Section, we present the implementation and the performance evaluation of the proposed orchestration framework. The experiments were carried out in the NETMODE⁵ testbed of the National Technical University of Athens, which is a small edge computing infrastructure.

We deployed two Kubernetes clusters, i.e., to simulate the edge and cloud infrastructure, using two OpenStack Virtual Machines (VMs) in two Intel Xeon Silver 4110 servers. Following the work in [46], the capacity of each server is $C_E = 8$ vCPUs, $R_E = 8$ GiB of RAM for the edge server and $C_C = 16$ vCPUs, $R_C = 16$ GiB of RAM for the cloud server. We consider that, for a fully functional server, the maximum power consumption is $P_{MAX}^E = 2000W$ and $P_{MAX}^C = 4000W$ as in [39]. The network communication between the two clusters is achieved by utilizing the Ligo open-source tool that allows the deployment of applications across multiple clusters. The OpenFaaS serverless platform handles the deployment of the serverless functions, while Prometheus enables the collection of metrics such as the end-to-end latency of the application or the incoming rate of requests to the function chain. We model the RL environment by using the OpenAI Gym library⁶ to create an interface so that our agents can interact with it, triggering scaling actions and receiving a reward in return. The interfaces that are used to actually interact with the testbed are those provided by the Kubernetes API⁷.

The evaluated function chain ($f_1 \rightarrow f_2 \rightarrow f_3$) is comprised by three services, which is a commonly-used graph, each performing a specific calculation on an input graph. Specifically, the first function performs a union on two randomly generated graphs, the second function performs link prediction on the output graph of the previous step adding the predicted edges and lastly, the third function calculates

⁵<https://www.fed4fire.eu/testbeds/netmode/>

⁶<https://www.gymnasium.dev/index.html>

⁷<https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/overview/kubernetes-api/>

the centralities of the nodes of the previous step. We assume that if a request takes more time than the maximum value for the latency defined in the selected SLA, then we have a QoS violation. This value is set to 0.5 seconds and regards the end-to-end latency for serving a request by the entire function chain. We selected that $R = 5$ Gb/s, as in [28], and the output of each function is $d = [1, 2, 1.5]$ Mbits for the three functions respectively. The high-level objective for the specific evaluation is considered to be "energy efficient" and "latency-sensitive" so we accordingly set $w_T = \frac{1}{3}$, $w_C = \frac{2}{3}$, $w_P = \frac{1}{6} \cdot 10^{-2}$. For the experiments, we selected that we invoke the RL-driven Autoscaler and the Scheduling Optimizer every 30 seconds.

To create an HTTP load for our application, the Vegeta tool was used, while for the generated workload we use the HTTP traces of the NASA server (Figure 7), as it is collected and analyzed in [47]. For the forecasting mechanism, we have used an ARIMA(p, d, q) model. The parameters have been set to $p = 2, d = 0, q = 3$ after comparing different combinations and selecting one with relatively high accuracy. We use 2/3 of this dataset for training of the RL-driven autoscaler and the ARIMA-based workload predictor and the last 1/3 for evaluating the framework's overall performance.

The source code for the implementation of the RL environment, the scheduling mechanism, the forecasting mechanism and the developed distributed application is made available as open-source at a GitLab repository⁸.

4.1. DQN agent training

The training of the DQN agent has taken place using the standard technique of collecting past data in a replay buffer and taking samples of it to train the neural network. The number of steps inside an epoch has been selected to match the seasonality of the data. At first, the replay buffer is filled with initial data collected over 100 epochs. Moreover, for the incoming workload λ , and the predicted workload $\bar{\lambda}$, a state-space reduction is also performed. Specifically, we characterize the workload by quantizing it at every 20 requests per second, to discretize the values. The learning rate α has been set to 0.001, the discount factor γ has been set to 0.9, and the probability of selecting a random value ϵ during the training phase has been set to 0.8. Additionally, a target network is created as a copy of the Q-network and is updated every 5 epochs. Given that the amount of data and time required to train the DQN agent is significantly large, the training was performed offline. The application graph was instantiated and stressed for various workloads collecting metrics regarding the application performance and state. Afterward, these metrics were used in conjunction with the training dataset to synthetically generate the environment state and speed up the training process. As a result, the decision can be provided in real-time. To measure the performance and accuracy of the learning process, evaluation data is collected at regular intervals during the training phase using a purely greedy policy based on the optimal Q values.

Figure 8: DQN training.

⁸<https://gitlab.com/netmode/intent-driven-serverless>

Table 2: Comparative table of autoscaling solutions.

Algorithm	% of latency violations				Number of replicas			
	min	max	mean	std	min	max	mean	std
DQN	1.29	1.79	1.52	0.21	10.36	10.49	10.44	0.06
PPO	10.87	11.10	10.95	0.10	9.67	10.15	9.98	0.21
Knative Concurrency	1.48	5.31	2.78	1.79	7.67	10.12	8.50	1.15

Figure 9: Percentage of requests that violated the SLA.

Figure 10: Sum of deployed replicas across all the microservices.

The evaluation results from the training process of the DQN agent are depicted in Figure 8, where each data point of the plot represents the average value of 3 evaluation epochs. It is noticed that the number of replicas is progressively reduced for all the microservices (see Figure 8a), while the reward converges in a value close to 70 (see Figure 8c). A reward value around 70 is considered satisfactory, given that we provide negative rewards (value of -100) in case of SLA violations. Due to the initial over-provisioning of resources, the number of violations stays really low in the beginning. Once the agent learns that the optimal strategy is to keep a balance between the number of deployed resources and the conformance to the SLA with regards to the latency value, the overall resources are progressively scaled down and some latency violations are observed (see Figure 8b).

4.2. Experiment A - Autoscaling Comparison

We evaluate the proposed framework, hereinafter referred to as DQN Reinforcement Learning and Scheduling (DRLS), with other baseline techniques, namely; (a) DRLFF: we utilize the proposed scaling decision by the DQN but we use a First Fit algorithm for the scheduling part as in [48], (b) PPO: we evaluate a Proximal Policy Optimization [49] algorithm in the place of DQN while employing our Scheduling Optimizer for the placement of functions, (c) CS: we utilize the concurrency autoscaling algorithm that is used in Knative⁹ with static placement of the functions, where autoscaling is based on

the number of concurrent in-flight requests that is a standard solution in the context of serverless computing.

In the proposed DRLS framework, a scaling decision is made every 30 seconds leaving enough time for the replicas to be instantiated. In all three scenarios, a limit of 1vCPU has been set. The concurrency metric for the Knative Pod Autoscaler (KPA) has been set to 3 concurrent requests. This value has been selected after testing multiple values and choosing one that balances application performance with respect to the observed latency and the number of provisioned resources. In all three cases a synthetic workload of 300 timesteps was created whose values were used to generate an HTTP load for our application. The first 120 values were selected directly from the evaluation dataset, while the remaining 180 values were created with additional noise to form a more dynamic evaluation setting. To quantify the comparison between the different methods, 10 evaluation runs were performed and aggregated in Table 2 depicting the minimum, maximum, and mean values as well as the standard deviation.

In Figure 9, we depict the percentage of requests that either violated the SLA for the latency metric or were not successfully processed from the DRLS, PPO, and CS mechanisms. It is shown that DRLS achieves better performance with an average of 1.52% violations compared to PPO which has 10.95% violations and CS which has 2.78% violations.

Moreover, in Figure 10 we present the number of active replicas for the entire function chain in the cases of DRLS, PPO and CS. On average DRLS requires 10.44 replicas while PPO and Knative deploy 9.98 and 8.50 replicas, respectively. It

⁹<https://knative.dev/docs/>

is noticed that DRLS over-provisions resources during periods of low stress while Knative and PPO manage to handle the load with fewer resources. This is an interesting outcome regarding potential improvements in the DRLS framework to better manage the number of deployed replicas in the scaling requests. Such improvements may be achieved through more extensive training of the DQN agent, or by interplaying with the assigned weights in the requests. Stability in the performance of emerging serverless computing platforms can be also considered an issue, since in our case we noticed bottlenecks in the efficient serving of the incoming requests in high workloads, independently of the scaling actions. This may be due to configuration aspects, since up to our knowledge, there are very few implementations that integrate solutions for multi-cluster management of computing resources with solutions for management of serverless function chains.

4.3. Experiment B - Scheduling Comparison

In Figure 11, a comparative evaluation between DRLS and DRLFF is shown regarding the total transformation cost, estimated as the number of migrations from the edge to the cloud and vice versa. The evaluation workload is the same as in the previous section. One can notice that DRLS outperforms DRLFF in terms of cost achieving 22% lower cost, leading to better placement decisions and reducing overhead of further delays due to the migration of resources, along with less power and better link utilization delay. Such functionality is considered crucial for the runtime management of applications across distributed resources in the computing continuum. Moreover, in Figure 12 we present evaluation results for the power consumption required in the cases of the DRLS and DRLFF mechanisms. It is shown that DRLS outperforms DRLFF by achieving 24.2% less power consumption throughout the experiment. Specifically, the measured energy consumed by the DRLFF and the DRLS mechanisms is 10.9KWhs and 8.3KWhs respectively. The average value of the total power consumed for the DRLFF algorithm was 4360W while for the DRLS algorithm it was 3303W.

Finally, we evaluated the proposed framework (DRLS) to the compared one, i.e., DRLFF (First Fit) in terms of average runtime and convergence to the optimal solution. The optimal solution to optimization Problem (13) is calculated with a brute force technique. As shown, in Fig. 13, we evaluate the two methods for different numbers of functions n . The proposed method calculates solutions that are close to the optimal ones (most of the time equals the optimal) and outperforms the DRLFF significantly whose convergence drops significantly, i.e. even to 0.1 ratio compared to the optimal case, as the number of functions increases. We would like to comment that we believe that the GUROBI solver finds most of the time the optimal value as the state space of the problem is relatively small as also stated in Section 3.5. Finally, the running time of the DRLS is almost linear for a small number of functions while the brute force grows exponentially as the number of functions increases.

Figure 11: Total cost.

Figure 12: Total power consumption.

4.4. Experiment C - Framework Evaluation

To further investigate the sensitivity of our framework to the values of the different hyper-parameters, a comparative evaluation was performed for the most important ones. In Table 3 we present the evaluation results for different values of the discount factor γ and the hyper-parameter g of the reward regarding the latency as defined in Eq. (11). We want to remind the reader that, in our setting g is set to 5 and the discount factor γ is set to 0.9.

Reducing γ to 0.8 leads to the deployment of more replicas and as a consequence fewer QoS violations. By lowering the value of γ , the agent learns to prioritize the short-term reward. In our case, we penalize the QoS violations more than deploying additional replicas. As a result, in this case, the agent prefers to avoid QoS violations i.e., to 0.48% of all requests, even at the cost of the under-utilization of the deployed replicas, as on average throughout the experiment we observe a higher value, i.e. 10.99. Furthermore, setting γ to 0.99 makes the agent value future rewards more, trying

Figure 13: Convergence to optimal solution and running time.

Table 3: Comparative table of different hyper-parameter values of the proposed framework.

Configuration	% of latency violations	Number of replicas
($g=5, \gamma=0.9$)	1.52	10.44
($g=5, \gamma=0.8$)	0.48	10.99
($g=5, \gamma=0.99$)	0.40	11.05
($g=1, \gamma=0.9$)	0.10	11.15
($g=10, \gamma=0.9$)	2.30	10.22

to minimize the QoS violations under the high fluctuating incoming workload. Hence, the number of deployed replicas is also increased, having an average of almost 11 throughout the experiment, naturally reducing the overall QoS violations, to 0.4%. As a result, the agent prefers the long-term decision of keeping more replicas deployed thus being prepared for spikes in the incoming workload. The value of 0.9 that we selected, finds a balance between the other two scenarios ultimately leading to fewer resources deployed, i.e., 10.44, with the trade-off of slightly increased to 1.52%, however acceptable, QoS violations.

Regarding the parameter g that determines the slope of the reward function as shown in Figure 6, a lower value of $g = 1$ signifies that the agent is penalized less for having a latency that is far from the specified SLA. As a result, the agent overprovisions resources (on average 11.15 replicas) which leads to really low values of latency, having only 0.1% QoS violations for all requests. On the other hand, increasing the value of $g = 10$ yields the opposite effect. The agent is penalized for staying away from the specified SLA value for the latency and learns that fewer resources, specifically 10.22 on average, lead to a higher reward with the drawback of increased violations (2.3% of all requests) during periods of higher workload. The selected value of 5 leverages the aforementioned information to optimally guide the agent toward better decisions that balance application performance and resource usage.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper, we have detailed an approach for intent-driven orchestration of serverless applications, considering the deployment and management of serverless function chains across multi-cluster infrastructure in the computing continuum. Focus is given on the translation of SLOs to an optimal deployment plan and the efficient scaling and - if required- migration of the deployed functions in resources in edge and cloud computing clusters. ML mechanisms and specifically RL is exploited to guide the autoscaling mechanisms while considering the input provided by workload forecasting techniques. A realistic deployment in a multi-cluster infrastructure based on the usage of open-source frameworks for multi-cluster management and serverless applications management has been provided and a set of experiments have taken place.

It is shown that the proposed approach can efficiently manage the deployment of serverless applications over multi-cluster resources based on the proper interpretation of the declared intent and its translation to orchestration actions. High conformance with the defined SLAs is achieved, by properly adjusting the allocated resources to the dynamic workload to avoid SLA violations. The provided scheduling mechanisms outperform existing static scheduling mechanisms in terms of avoidance of migrations across the clusters and the associated costs, as well as in terms of the achieved energy efficiency. A need for improvement is also identified in the number of activated replicas based on the autoscaling decisions, especially in cases where the workload is not high.

Various open research areas have been identified for extending this work. Even if various approaches are promoting intent-driven orchestration for edge and cloud computing applications, there is a need for the specification of formal description languages for the intent, accompanied by intent translation mechanisms. In this way, the defined intent can be formally associated with SLOs and translated to SLAs that can be interpreted by intelligent orchestration mechanisms. Moreover, the orchestration of FaaS in the Cloud Continuum requires the collaboration of multi-agent systems for the resource management of the infrastructure. In the same direction, the optimal scheduling of function chains requires considering various constraints such as the bandwidth and or collocation for optimal placement or even the selection between heterogeneous resources e.g., CPUs, and GPUs, to optimize the performance of the functions. With regards to the autoscaling functions supported by RL mechanisms, an extension of the existing framework is envisaged to better tackle the overprovisioning of resources in some time periods. Finally, the evaluation of the presented framework in a computing environment that consists of multiple edge servers is also planned to better highlight the performance benefits of the proposed scheduling solution.

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